

Perception of Academic Staff Toward Transformation from Conventional to Digital base on Students Examination Record Management in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel

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ABSTRACT

The paper examines the attitude of academic staff toward shifting from the use of conventional institutional method of students' examination record management to the new development of recently introduced digital-based students' records management system (SRMS). Still some academic staff stick to the manual or conventional method of managing student examination record. However, academic staff from the school of science are more conversant to the utilization of digital-based students' examination record than academic staff from other schools. However, lack of efficient service or network provision and lack of effective computer literacy training among some academic staff are considered to be the major factors responsible toward sticking to the conventional method of managing student examination record instead of the computer base student record management system.

Keywords: Academic Staff Perception, Digital Transformation, Examination Record Management, Conventional to Digital Shift, Higher Education, Educational Technology, Jigawa State College of Education Gumel

Introduction

The field of record management has over the past two decades undergone great advancement and this is mainly due to the emergence of modern information Immunization technology. The adoption of ICT in education industry with particular reference to high institution of learning has improved both the administrative and academic duties of the institution, student examination record management inclusive.

Compared with manual methods, digital base student's examination record management drastically increases efficiency and reduces costs. Thus it is a highly effective and efficient way to upload, manage and retrieve examination stores and other related information pertaining to students with a shortest possible time and space.

Problem Statement Justification:

The adoption of ICT students Record Management System (SRMS) with particular reference to students examination record management in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel, which has been recognized as a welcome development by government and other stakeholders, but still not fully assimilated by some academic staff members. Many academic staff are still using the traditional or manual method in managing student examination record and result computation processes. This problem may not be unconnected to responsible factors such as lack of adequate or effective computer literacy training among some academic staff, poor server network provision, lack of enough competent and dedicated ICT personnel.

In addition, it would not be an overstatement to say that some academic staff have the habit of poor commitment to job and dedication to duty. And this consequently resulted to not being able to transform themselves into the current method of managing students' examination record of the digital base system resources. Therefore, there is a gross inadequate qualified and dedicated staff facilities, students' explosion and space problem. This study in therefore a response to the challenge by striving to empirically identify these problems and well-developed management options that could improve record keeping processes in Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel especially in the area of the study.

Research Questions

- Are the academic staff of JSCOE Gumel computer literate?
- Is there efficient network provision for SRMS portal in JSCOE Gumel?
- Are the ICT personnel of JSCOE Gumel competent and dedicated in discharging their duties?
- What is the difference between the academic staff from school of science and those from other school in terms of competency in using SRMS portal?

Objectives of the Study:

The main objectives of the study are:

- To find out the level of computer literacy training among the academic staff of the college
- To assess the efficiency of service provider or network provision for students result management system (SRMS) effectiveness.
- To find out the competency level and dedication attitude of the ICT personnel of the college.
- To find out the differences between academic staff of school of sciences and other schools in terms of competency level in using digital base students examination record management.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The Concept of Record Management

Records Management, also known as records and information management is an organisational function devoted to the management of information in an organization throughout his life cycle, from the time of creation.

Iso (2001) define record management as the field of management responsible for the efficient and systematic control of the creation, receipt, maintenance, use and disposition of records including the processes for capturing and maintaining evidence of and information about organisation activities and transaction in the form of record.

An organisation's record preserves aspects of institutional memory. In determining how long to retain records their capacity for re-use is important. Many are kept as evidence of activities, transactions, value judgement and decision.

The Concept of Information Communication Technology (ICT)

The term Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is a Confluence from Information Technology (IT) and communication Technology (CT). ICT is technology that support activities involving information. Such activities include gathering, processing, storing and presenting data. Increasingly these activities also involve collaboration and communication.

According to Khan et al (2015), Information Communication Technology refers to technology that provides access to information through communication. Also ICT is an umbrella term that includes any communication device, encompassing radio, television, cellphone, computers and network hardware, satellite systems, with then such as video conferencing, distance learning, e-learning. Learning management system and more important role of information and

communication technology (ICT) value through education that cannot be overemphasized in any society (Akarowhe, 2017).

Information and communication Technology on the other hand is a term that entails a lot of actions involving the acquisition, storage, processing and information dissemination through the use of suitable hardware and software designed for such purpose (Abubakar, 2010). It also refers to a range of technologies that are applied process of collecting, storing, editing, retrieving and transferring information in various forms.

The Role of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Education

The growing demand on educational institutions to information and communication technology in the planning, coordination, implementation, controlling, supervision and evaluation processes of its programmes and activities, signifies the remarkable position that ICT occupies in education industry in (ICT) and the internet, have been the (enabler) driving force behind new mode of teaching and learning process, students' performance, , evaluation, procedure and management of student record of performance and information, has transform the entire educational terrain and altered the educational system in a fundamental way (Aduwa-Ogiegbaen, 2013). ICT is therefore an important instrument in supporting and creating new methods of managing teaching and learning thereby developing students and instructors skills of cooperation, communication, problem and life-long learning. Thus, ICT integration is the blending of ICT into the whole school structure and functions of the school system.

Therefore, the application and use of ICT is beneficial in improving education system and giving academic staff a better and effective means for management of students' information and teaching experience and student a better education.

Challenges of using ICT in Education

Integrating ICT into educational institutions is a complex process and one that may encounter a number of difficulties. These difficulties are known as challenges. The following are some of the major challenges that have been identified regarding the use of ICT tools in education;

1. Limited accessibility and network connection
2. Lack of effective computer literacy training among academic staff
3. Limited time frame for instructions and activities or task accomplishment
4. Lack of adequate facilities and other necessary materials

The Concept of Digital Base Record Management

Digital base record management, otherwise known as electronic Record Management System (ERMS) is a computer program or set of programs used to track and store information. It is an electronic system that allows teachers or instructors to upload, record and peculiar information needed using scientifically developed portal or website. However electronic Record Management System (ERM S) is characterized by a number of features such as.

- Easy access
- Providing fast and continuous feedback or retrieval
- Taking amount of differences among student record/information
- Facilitating and improving service delivery.
- Saves time

METHODS, POPULATION, SAMPLE SIZE, STUDY AREA AND DATA COLLECTIONS

Research Design

The research study was descriptive survey design.

Population of the Study

The population of the study is the entire academic staff of Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.

Sample Size

The samples of the study are two (2) departments, Department of Integrated Science from Science and Department of Arabic from School of Languages. The Sample size of the students will be fifty (50) academic staff 25 from Integrated Science Department, 25 from Arabic Department. The sample technique is simple random selection from the selected departments.

Data collection Procedure

Data collection instrument for the study was questionnaire.

Data Analysis

The data analysis for the study was made through the use of means deviation

Result

Results (Expected Outputs Results).

The expected outputs of this study include the following:

- There is lack of effective computer literacy training among some academic staff of Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.
- There is problem of poor network connection with regard to the server providers of Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.
- There is lack of competency and dedication to duty by ICT personnel of Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.
- Academic staff from school of science may be more competent in using digital base students' examination record management than those from other school in Jigawa State College of Education Gumel.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

Research Question 1. Are the Academic Staff of JSCOE Gumel computer literate?

Table 1: Decision of 2.5, above factor, below not a factor

S/N	Items	SA4F	A3F	D2F	SD1F	X	Decision
1	There is frequent use of the SRMS portal by the academic staff	12	15	10	13	2.52	A factor accepted
2	There is regular staff training and seminar on the use of the portal for SRMS	19	18	7	6	2.98	A factor accepted
3	All academic staff are using their username and password to access the portal for SRMS themselves	4	05	18	23	1.72	Not a factor Rejected
4	The academic staff are confident in using portal for SRMS	9	6	20	15	2.18	Not a factor Rejected

Table 1 shows that there is regular academic staff training and seminars in JSCOE Gumel for the academic staff on the portal for SRMS as revealed by the respondents with the highest mean score of 2.98 which is a factor and accepted as it is above the decision of 2.5, but not all

academic staff are using their username and password to access the portal by themselves for SRMS as indicated by the respondents with the lowest mean score of 1.72, which is not a factor and rejected as it is below the decision of 2.5.

Research Question 2: Is there efficient network provision for SRMS portal in JSCOE Gumel?

S/N	Items	SA4F	A3F	D2F	SD1F	X	Decision
1	The SRMS portal of JSCOE Gumel accepts and process data with high speed	20	16	6	8	2.96	A factor accepted
2	There is prompt response to the challenges posed by the portal from the portal developers.	5	5	15	20	1.8	Not a factor Rejected
3	There is availability of internet services for the use of the portal	5	7	18	20	1.94	Not a Factor rejected

Table 2 shows that the portal of JSCOE Gumel for SRMS accepts and processes data with high speed as indicated by the responses which is above the decision of 2.5, but there is no prompt response to the challenges posed by the portal from the portal developers as revealed by the respondents with the lowest mean score of 1.8 which is not factor and rejected as it is below the decision of 2.5.

Research Question 3: Are the ICT personnel of JSCOE Gumel competent and dedicated?

Table 3: Decision of 2.5, above factor below not a factor

S/N	Items	SA4F	A3F	D2F	SD1F	X	Decision
1	ICT Personnel are technically groomed and competent in discharging their duties	20	13	10	7	2.92	A factor accepted
2	ICT personnel are willing and readily available to attend academic staff complaints	15	15	9	11	2.68	A factor accepted
3	ICT personnel liaises with directorate for quality assurance in enhancing the provision of their services	9	10	15	16	2.24	Not a factor rejected

Table 3 has made it clear that IT personnel of JSCOE Gumel are technically groomed and competent in discharging their duties as revealed by the respondent with the highest mean store of 2.92 which is a factor and accepted as it is above the decision of 2.5, but they do not liaised with the Directorate for Quality Assurance of the College to enhance the provision of their services as revealed by the respondents with the lowest mean store of 2.24 which is not a factor and rejected as it is below the decision of 2.5.

Research Question 4: What are the difference in competency level between the academic staff of school of science and other schools in using the portal for SRMS?

Table 4: Decision of 2.5, above factor below not a factor

S/N	Items	SA4F	A3F	D2F	SD1F	X	Decision
1	Academic staff from the school of science are more competent in using the portal for SRMS than other staff from different school	20	18	08	4	3.08	A factor accepted
2	Academic staff of the school of science shares the same level with their colleagues from other schools in the use if the portal	4	10	15	21	1.94	Not a factor Rejected
3	Academic staff from other school seek support and technical assistance from their colleagues of the school of science in using the portal for SRMS.	16	14	12	8	2.76	A factor Accepted

Table 4 shows that academic staff from school of science differ significantly in term competency level in using the portal for SRMS with those from other schools as indicated by the respondents with the highest mean score of 3.08 which is a factor and accepted as it is above the decision of 2.5, but they do not share the same level with their colleagues of other schools in the frequent use of the portal for SRMS as revealed by the respondents with the lowest mean score of 1.94 which is not a factor and rejected as it is below the decision of 2.5.

Summary of the Findings

1. There is Provision of regular training and Seminar for HR Portal for SRM
2. The SRMS Portal of JSCOE Gumel accepts and processes data with high speed.
3. ICT Personnel at JSCOE Gumel are technically groomed and competent in discharging their duties.
4. Academic staff of JSCOE Gumel from School of Science are more competent than those from other Schools in using the portal for SRMS.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of the Study

The study was conducted to identify the perception of academic staff toward the transformation from conventional to digital-based Student Examination Record Management in Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel. Section two discussed the concept of record management, the concept of Information and Communication Technology (ICT), the role of ICT in education, and the concept of digital-based record management. Section three highlighted the methodology, population and sample size, study area, and data collection procedure. Section four presented the analysis of the study, including the summary of data, research questions answered, and results presented using frequency and mean deviation. The findings were summarized and discussed. And finally section five focused on the summary, conclusion, and recommendations from the study, as well as suggestions for further research.

Conclusion

The study conducted has shown that there is frequent use of the SRMS portal by the academic staff of JSCOGE Gumel, indicating their level of computer literacy. However, most academic staff do not use their login credentials themselves but assign junior staff to upload results on their behalf.

Similarly the study has revealed that the SRMS Portal of JSCOGE Gumel has an efficient network provision, accepting and processing data at high speed. However, there is a problem of poor response from the portal developers in addressing challenges.

The study also revealed that the ICT Personnel at JSCOGE Gumel are competent and dedicated, discharging their duties with expertise. However they do not collaborate sufficiently with the Directorate for Quality Assurance to enhance service delivery.

The study also revealed that academic staff from the School of Sciences are more competent in using the portal for SRMS compared to those from other schools, indicating a significant difference in technical skills in using the portal for SRMS.

Recommendations

Recommendations from the Study

The following recommendations were made for the study:

1. Though there is frequent use of SRMS portal by the academic staff, they should also be encouraged to use their username and password by themselves in accessing the portal for SRMS.
2. That SRMS portal accepts and processes data with high speed, there is need for the portal developers to promptly respond to the challenges posed by the portal.
3. Though ICT Personnel of JSCOE Gumel are technically groomed and competent in discharging their duties, yet they should work closely with the Directorate for Quality Assurance to improve service delivery.
4. Though Academic staff from school of science are competent in using the portal for SRMS, those from other schools should be encouraged to seek technical assistance from more competent academic staff.

Recommendations for Further Study

The research suggested further research work in the following areas.

1. Ways to encourage academic staff of JSCOE Gumel to use their login are credentials independently.
2. An assessment of the role of SRMS Portal developers in resolving challenges faced in JSCOE Gumel.

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